

EFFECT OF NUTRITION EDUCATION PROGRAMME ON NUTRITIONAL KNOWLEDGE OF RURAL MOTHERS RESIDING IN AGRA DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Mothers play a vital role in maintaining the nutritional well-being of their families, especially in rural areas where knowledge gaps often contribute to poor health outcomes. Limited awareness about proper nutrition, hygiene, and food practices can lead to undernutrition and related issues in young children. This study aimed to assess the impact of nutrition education on improving the nutritional knowledge of mothers residing in rural parts of the Agra district. A total of 192 mothers aged 20–35 years, each with a child under six years, participated in the study. A self-structured questionnaire was used to evaluate their knowledge across five areas: undernutrition, balanced diet, food sources, nutrient preservation, and hygiene. A one-month educational intervention was conducted, and knowledge levels were compared before and after the program. The results showed a significant increase in knowledge across all domains, particularly in undernutrition and hygiene. The study concludes that structured, locally relevant nutrition education can be effective in increasing awareness among rural mothers and can play an important role in promoting healthier dietary practices and child care.

Keywords: Nutrition education, Rural areas, Mothers, Nutritional knowledge, Children

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Nutritional knowledge among mothers plays a vital role in ensuring the health and well-being of families, particularly in rural areas where malnutrition remains a pressing issue. Mothers, as primary caregivers, significantly influence household food choices, meal preparation, and child feeding practices. However, in many rural parts of India, including the Agra district of Uttar Pradesh, limited access to information, low literacy levels, and socio-cultural factors often result

in poor dietary practices and inadequate nutritional awareness (Kumar et al., 2021). Nutrition education is an important public health strategy that aims to improve individuals' knowledge and skills regarding food, health, and nutrition. It helps mothers understand the importance of balanced diets, food groups, micronutrient requirements, and hygienic practices, thereby enabling them to make informed decisions about their family's nutrition (Roy et al., 2020). Studies have demonstrated that community-based nutrition education interventions can lead to measurable improvements in knowledge and behavior, particularly among women in low-resource settings (Yadav & Singh, 2022). The Indian government has introduced several initiatives such as the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) and POSHAN Abhiyaan to combat malnutrition by promoting awareness and behavior change through local outreach programs (Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2021). Despite these efforts, gaps in knowledge and practice persist, particularly in rural areas where program reach and impact may be limited.

2.0. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the socio-demographic profile of rural mothers.
2. To assess the nutrition knowledge of rural mothers.
3. To evaluate the effect of the nutrition education programme on the nutrition knowledge of rural mothers.

3.0.METHODOLOGY

The present study employed an experimental research design using a one-group pre-test post-test approach in rural areas of the Agra district. The study included 192 mothers aged 20–35 years, each having at least one child under 6 years of age, selected through purposive sampling. A self-structured and validated questionnaire was used to assess nutritional knowledge before and after the intervention. The intervention consisted of a one-month nutrition education program, delivered weekly through lectures and discussions in the local language, covering topics like undernutrition, balanced diet, food sources, preservation of nutrients and hygiene. Pre- and post-intervention data were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics and a paired *t*-test to evaluate changes in knowledge. Ethical clearance was obtained, and informed consent was taken from all participants.

4.0.RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The study aimed to assess the effect of a one-month nutrition education intervention on the nutritional knowledge of 192 mothers in rural areas of Agra. The analysis focused on five key domains: undernutrition, balanced diet, food sources, preservation of nutrients, and hygiene. Pre- and post-intervention scores were compared using paired *t*-tests to measure the effectiveness of the intervention.

Table 4.1. Distribution of the socio-demographic profile of the rural mothers

Variables	Categories	Number (N=192)	Percentage (%)
Age	20-25	68	35.41
	26-30	79	41.14
	31- 35	45	23.43
Religion	Hindu	148	77.08
	Muslim	44	22.91
Education	Graduate	12	6.25
	Intermediate	29	15.10
	High school	38	19.79
	Primary school	54	28.12
	Illiterate	59	30.72
Occupation	Working	54	28.12
	House wives	138	71.87
Monthly income in rupees	<5000	38	19.79
	5001-10,000	65	33.85
	>10,000	89	46.35
Type of family	Nuclear	13	6.77
	Joint	87	45.31
	Extended	92	47.91

The above table illustrates the socio-demographic profile of 192 mothers from rural areas of Agra district, aged between 20 and 35 years. A large proportion of respondents (41.14%) fell in the 26–30 year age group, followed by 35.41% in the 20–25 year range. This indicates that most participants were in their active reproductive phase, which is a crucial period for receiving nutrition education. Similar findings were reported by Yadav and Singh (2022), who noted that younger mothers tend to be more open to adopting new health-related behaviors.

The religious distribution showed that a majority (77.08%) were Hindu, with the remaining 22.91% identifying as Muslim. In terms of educational attainment, a significant number of participants had low literacy levels, with 30.72% being illiterate and 28.12% educated only up to the primary level. These results are consistent with the study by Agarwal et al. (2019), which highlighted limited formal education among rural mothers as a barrier to nutritional awareness and child care practices. Roy et al. (2020) also observed that low education levels often lead to poor understanding of dietary requirements, reinforcing the importance of accessible nutrition education.

Most of the mothers (71.87%) were homemakers, indicating their central role in food preparation and child-rearing. This finding supports the view of Dasgupta et al. (2020), who emphasized that housewives in rural households are key influencers of family dietary habits and are well-positioned to benefit from nutrition education programs when delivered appropriately.

In terms of economic status, 46.35% of participants had a monthly household income above ₹10,000, while 33.85% earned between ₹5,001 and ₹10,000. A smaller group (19.79%) reported income below ₹5,000, suggesting that a considerable proportion of the sample belonged to economically constrained households. Similar observations were made by Kumar et al. (2021), who noted that limited income in rural settings often restricts access to a diverse and balanced diet, highlighting the need for low-cost, nutrition-rich food strategies.

The family structure analysis showed that most respondents lived in extended (47.91%) and joint families (45.31%), while only 6.77% were part of nuclear households. This trend aligns with traditional rural living arrangements in India. Research by Yadav and Singh (2022) suggests that in joint or extended families, food-related decisions are often made collectively, which can influence how new nutritional practices are adopted or resisted.

Figure 4.2. Assessment of nutritional knowledge of mothers

The domain-wise analysis of mean scores provides insight into specific areas of nutritional knowledge among the 192 rural mothers included in the study. As shown in the table, the scores varied across the five categories assessed. The highest mean score (4.98) was observed in the domain of hygiene, indicating that mothers were most informed about cleanliness and sanitation practices. This may be attributed to national awareness campaigns and increased community outreach on sanitation in recent years. Similar observations were made by Bhattacharya et al. (2020) in their study on hygiene awareness in rural households, where mothers demonstrated relatively high knowledge in personal and food hygiene compared to other domains of nutrition. In contrast, knowledge about balanced diets was found to be the lowest (1.69), revealing a significant gap in understanding the importance of food variety, nutrient combinations, and daily dietary planning. This aligns with the findings of Nair and Joseph (2019), who reported that rural women often struggle to differentiate between food groups and lack the knowledge required to

construct a balanced plate, primarily due to limited exposure to formal nutrition education. The domain of undernutrition showed a moderate score (3.04), suggesting partial awareness about the signs and consequences of nutrient deficiencies, particularly in children. However, a deeper understanding of the causes and prevention strategies was limited. A study conducted by Rani et al. (2021) supports this trend, indicating that while many rural mothers recognize visible symptoms like weight loss or fatigue, they are less aware of underlying causes such as inadequate feeding practices or low-quality diets. In the area of food sources, the mean score was 2.83, indicating some level of knowledge about origin and types of food, although not comprehensive. This could be influenced by direct involvement in agriculture or household food procurement, as also noted by Dev and Sharma (2022), who found that rural women's knowledge of staple foods was stronger than that of nutrient-dense or fortified foods. Lastly, preservation of nutrients scored 3.28, reflecting a fair understanding of cooking and storage techniques that help retain the nutritional value of food. Mothers showed awareness of some traditional practices, though scientific methods were less understood. This is consistent with the findings of Pathak and Kumari (2018), who observed that while many rural households follow practices like covering food and avoiding re-heating, they are unaware of modern strategies such as pressure steaming or minimal water cooking.

Table 4.2. Effect of nutrition education on nutritional knowledge of mothers of children from the pre-intervention phase to the post-intervention phase

Domains of Nutritional Knowledge	Pre-intervention (Mean±SD)	Post-intervention (Mean±SD)	t-value	p-value
Undernutrition	3.04±0.76	7.40±0.85	48.80	<0.001***
Balanced Diet	1.69±1.77	4.43±0.99	31.93	<0.001***
Food sources	2.83±1.95	6.57±0.78	29.76	<0.001***
Preservation of Nutrients	3.28±1.98	7.18±1.04	26.07	<0.001***
Hygiene	4.98±1.98	9.29±2.37	26.33	<0.001***

Note: “p” indicates the level of significance, p<0.001 means Highly significant (*).**

The above findings reveal that before the intervention, the average pre-intervention scores were low in all five domains. The lowest pre-intervention score (1.69) was recorded in the balanced diet domain, suggesting limited awareness about dietary diversity and the role of various food groups in daily nutrition. This aligns with findings by Kamble and Choudhary (2021), who reported that rural women often lack clarity on what constitutes a balanced diet, primarily due to low education and limited access to nutrition information. After the intervention, this domain showed a significant increase to 4.43, demonstrating that focused education can successfully address these gaps.

Similarly, the undernutrition domain, which initially had a mean score of 3.04, rose sharply to 7.40. This improvement reflects increased understanding of undernutrition's causes,

symptoms, and prevention. Sahu et al. (2020) also noted similar improvements in their study in rural Odisha, where mothers displayed enhanced recognition of undernutrition after engaging in hands-on nutrition education sessions.

Knowledge of food sources improved from 2.83 to 6.57, indicating that mothers became more aware of nutrient-dense foods and their origin. This mirrors the findings of Pandey and Mishra (2022), who observed a shift in food choice behavior following home-based nutrition awareness programs, especially when local food items were used as teaching examples.

The domain of nutrient preservation also showed strong progress, with scores increasing from 3.28 to 7.18. This reflects greater awareness of cooking and storage methods that retain nutritional value. Similar findings were reported by Chakraborty and Das (2019), who highlighted that after practical demonstrations, rural caregivers adopted better food handling techniques such as steaming and avoiding overcooking.

The hygiene domain, which had the highest baseline knowledge (4.98), improved significantly to 9.29. This may be due to prior exposure to government-led sanitation drives, which the intervention further reinforced. The findings are supported by Bhattacharya et al. (2020), who documented that mothers in rural areas already possessed moderate hygiene knowledge due to public health campaigns but benefited from targeted reminders and demonstrations.

Across all domains, the high *t-values* and *p-values* below 0.001 confirm that the nutrition education intervention had a statistically significant impact on knowledge enhancement. The gains were particularly remarkable in domains where initial knowledge was low, validating the need for such community-level programs.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that nutrition education has a positive and significant impact on the knowledge of rural mothers regarding essential nutrition topics. After the intervention, participants showed marked improvement in their understanding of undernutrition, hygiene, balanced diet, food sources, and methods of preserving nutrients. This suggests that a well-structured educational program can effectively bridge knowledge gaps among mothers with limited formal education. Empowering mothers with accurate nutrition information not only enhances their awareness but also contributes to better nutritional care for their children. Integrating such interventions into rural health outreach can play a vital role in addressing malnutrition and promoting healthier communities.

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